

Enhancing Students' Motivation and Self-Efficacy Belief in Solving Biology Related Problems using Frequent Practical Work

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Abstract

The study investigated if frequent practical work could enhance senior secondary two (SS2) students' motivation and self-efficacy belief in solving Biology related problem. A sample of 141 Senior Secondary 2 Students from three government-approved schools in Konshisha Local Government Area of Benue State Nigeria was used. The study adopted non-equivalent quasi-experimental research design. The instruments used for data collection was Biology Motivation Questionnaire (BMQ) and Biology Self-Efficacy Belief Scale (BSEBS) with the reliability value of 0.86 and 0.89 using Cronbach Alpha respectively. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The research questions were answered using Mean and Standard Deviation scores while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Analysis of Covariance. The study revealed that there is significant difference in the mean motivation scores among students in the harmonized, intermediate, and control groups [$F_{2, 135}=368.100, P<0.05$]. It was also found that there is significant difference in the mean self-efficacy belief scores among students in the harmonized, intermediate, and control groups [$F_{2, 135}=376.009, P<0.05$]. It is recommended among others that teachers should be encouraged to use frequent practical to enhance students' motivation and self-efficacy belief in solving Biology related problem. Workshops and seminars should be organized for biology teachers to keep them abreast of the practical work. This will enable them to plan and organize adequately for practical work.

Keywords: Frequent practical work, motivation, self-efficacy belief, biology related problems.

Introduction

Practical work in school is carried out in different ways. In this study, practical work refers to biology teaching and learning activity which at some point involves the biology students (individually or collaboratively) in observing and/or manipulating the objects or materials they are studying. The observation and/or manipulation of objects might take place in a school biology laboratory or within the classroom. Practical work puts the students at the center of learning where they can participate in, rather than be told about biology in theory. Practical work can motivate pupils by stimulating interest and enhance the learning of scientific

knowledge and self-efficacy belief in solving biology related problem. Practical work plays an important role in science and biology teaching in particular. Several researchers such as Garnett and Hacking (2015); Ajayi and Ogbeba (2017) suggest that students will be more successful through participation in practical activities in the classroom or science laboratory.

Similarly, Hodson cited in Sani (2013) opine that, if the purpose of practical work is to gain an understanding of scientific investigation, then learning about science has to be linked with doing science. Practical work is about "learning by doing" and would confirm the theory presented in the textbooks (Moed, 2010). Practical work delivered with flair

and knowledge can help pupils understand scientific concepts and ignite their motivation to learn biology. Practical work provides students with opportunities for understanding and manipulating the complex and abstract nature of science in inducing effective conceptual change. In the same vein, practical work is also an important part of scientific knowledge and teaches pupils about the empirical basis of scientific enquiry and thereby ignites their self-efficacy belief in solving biology related problems. The researchers observed with dismay that what is happening presently in Nigeria secondary schools especially in the study area is that students are not frequently exposed to laboratory practical work.

In the same vein, Achor and Agamber (2013) observed that science teachers in general and Biology teachers in particular hardly conduct practical work with students. In some schools from Senior Secondary one (SS1) to Senior Secondary three (SS3), only few practical works are carried out with students. In some others, students are privileged to have access to practical work only when teachers have collected specimens for Senior School Certificate Examinations (SSCE) (West African Examination Council, WAEC and National Examination Council, NECO). The authors' observation was also affirmed by (WAEC) Chief Examiners report on Biology result in 2017 that among the reasons listed for the students' poor achievement is total negligence of practical lessons by teachers. The researchers opines that if the biology teachers will serve their purpose successfully, then students must be actively involved in doing, thinking, and evolving solutions to biology related problem and thereby ignite their motivation to learn and self-efficacy belief.

By implication, students' motivation to learn and self-efficacy belief

in solving biology related problem may be enhance if exposed to frequent and good practical lessons or experiments. The more frequent an activity is learned and carried out, the more permanent one is likely to master it. Motivation refers to the way in which urges, drives, desires, aspirations and strivings or needs influence the choice of alternatives in the behaviour of human beings. Motivation refers to the internal mode of an organism that causes to direct his/her behavior toward a goal. Motivation is activate factor of human behaviour (Seyf, 2009). Students are motivated to learn and achieve when they perceive their teachers care about them. Teachers who care were described as demonstrating democratic interaction styles, developing practical activities that can enhance scientific understanding of concept, and providing constructive feedback. Self-efficacy belief is one's belief about one's capability to successfully accomplish a task (Bandura, 2012).

Self-efficacy belief is defined self-efficacy as people's judgment about their ability to organize and carry out some behaviour in order to reach predetermined goals. In other words, self-efficacy belief is related to the way students judge their academic competence. People with high self-efficacy belief consider difficult tasks as challenges which they can overcome. These individuals choose challenging tasks, recover their self-efficacy faster, and keep on trying in spite of difficulties. Conversely, Gassner (2015) revealed that individuals with low self-efficacy beliefs tend to avoid tasks that they think or believe they do not have the capabilities to accomplish. The role of students' self-efficacy belief in solving science related problem continues to intrigue researchers. Thus, question is; does frequent practical work have anything to do with students' motivation to learn and their self-efficacy belief in solving biology related-problems?

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate if frequent practical work could improve students' motivation and self-efficacy belief in solving Biology related problem. Specifically, the study;

1. Investigate if frequent practical work could enhance students' motivation.
2. Investigate if frequent practical work could enhance students' self-efficacy belief.

Research Questions

Three research questions guided this study:

1. What are the mean motivation scores of students' in the harmonized, intermediate and control groups?
2. What are the mean self-efficacy belief scores of students' in the harmonized, intermediate and control groups?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided this study:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean motivation scores among students in the harmonized, intermediate and control groups.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean self-efficacy belief scores among students in the harmonized, intermediate and control groups.

Research Design and Procedure

The study used pre-test, post-test non-equivalent quasi experimental design. The design was considered appropriate because intact classes were used. The study area was Konshisha Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised all the 2,918 SSI students in the 27 government approved secondary schools.

A sample of 141 students was purposively sampled from three schools that had at least some basic equipment and facilities meant for this research and Biology teachers. The three schools were assigned randomly to group A (Harmonized group), group B (Intermediate group) and group C (Control group).

Group A is the harmonized group. In this group all lessons were accompanied with practical or experiments for the duration of six weeks of teaching. Group B is the intermediate group which consists of Biology students who were taught the theory aspect of Biology for six weeks and within this duration only two practical sessions were conducted. Group C is the control group which consists of Biology students who were taught only the theory aspect of Biology for a period of six weeks but no practical was conducted in any of the lessons or periods. Three research assistants were employed and trained by the researcher for three days to teach the instructional units before the treatment. Instruments known as Biology Motivation Questionnaire (BMQ) and Biology Self-Efficacy Belief Scale (BSEBS) was developed by the researchers and validated by three experts in science education and one expert in measurement and evaluation all from Benue State University, Makurdi was used to collect the data.

Biology Motivation Questionnaire (BMQ) contained two sections. Section "A" contained demographic information of the respondents, while section "B" contained a 14-item questionnaire which is intended to help students express their motivation to learn Biology. Each of the items is a 4-point Likert-rating scale with 4 response options. The options are Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). BMQ is a 4-Likert scale with number indicators as 4 (strongly agree), 3 (agree), 2 (disagree) and 1 (strongly disagree). BMQ were administered twice as pre-test and post-test. The reason for Pre-BMQ and Post-

BMQ is to ascertain students' motivation before and after treatment.

Meanwhile, Biology Self-Efficacy Belief Scale (BSEBS) contained two sections. Section "A" contained demographic information of the respondents, while section "B" contained a 25-item questionnaire which is intended to help students express their belief or confidence in solving Biology related problems. Each of the items is a 4-point Likert-rating scale with 4 response options. The options are Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Moderate Extent (ME), and Low Extent (LE). BSEBS is a 4-Likert scale with number indicators as 4 (Very High Extent), 3 (High Extent), 2 (Moderate Extent) and 1 (Low Extent)

The items were developed from information acquired through review of relevant literature by the researcher.

Table 1: Mean Motivation and Standard Deviation Scores of Students' in Harmonized, Intermediate and Control Groups

Group	N	PRE- BMQ		POST- BMQ		Mean Gain within Group
		\bar{x}	δ	\bar{x}	δ	
Harmonized group	42	1.17	0.13	3.87	0.11	2.70
Control group	51	1.15	0.15	2.11	0.14	0.96
Mean diff. between Groups		0.02		1.76		1.74
Intermediate group	48	1.16	0.14	3.83	0.13	2.67
Control group	51	1.15	0.15	2.11	0.14	0.96
Mean diff. between Groups		0.01		1.72		0.71
Harmonized group	42	1.17	0.13	3.87	0.11	2.70
Intermediate group	48	1.16	0.14	3.83	0.13	2.67
Mean diff. between Groups		0.01		0.04		0.03

Source: Field Survey, 2018

BSEBS was administered twice as pre-test and post-test though reshuffled. The reason for Pre-BSEBS and Post-BSEBS was to ascertain students' self-efficacy belief before and after treatment. Cronbach Alpha was used to obtain the BMQ and BSEBS reliability, which yielded a coefficient value of 0.86 and 0.89 respectively. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation scores while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses.

Results

Research question one

What are the mean motivation scores of students' in the harmonized, intermediate and control groups? The answer to research question one is contained in Table 1.

Table 1 reveals the mean motivation scores of students in the harmonized, intermediate and control groups on a paired comparative basis. The data in table 1 show that the overall mean difference between students in harmonized and control groups was 1.74 in favour of harmonized group. This implies that students in harmonized group had higher motivation than students in control group. Similarly, the overall mean difference between students in intermediate and control groups was 0.71 in favour of intermediate group. This implies that students in intermediate group had higher motivation than those in control group. In the same vein, the overall mean difference between students in harmonized and

intermediate groups was 0.03. This difference is in favour of harmonized group. This implies that students in harmonized group had higher motivation than their counterparts in intermediate group. Thus, it can be concluded that the more frequently practical is conducted along with theory lessons in Biology; the more students are motivated to learn Biology.

Research question two

What is the mean self-efficacy belief scores of students’ in the harmonized, intermediate and control groups? The answer to research question two is contained in Table 2.

Table 2: Mean Self-Efficacy Belief and Standard Deviation Scores of Students’ in Harmonized, Intermediate and Control groups

Group	N	PRE- BSEBS \bar{x}	δ	POST- BSEBS \bar{x}	δ	Mean Gain within Group
Harmonized group	42	1.10	0.11	3.74	0.14	2.64
Control group	51	1.07	0.13	2.27	0.12	1.20
Mean diff. between Groups		0.03		1.47		1.44
Intermediate group	48	1.09	0.15	3.70	0.16	2.61
Control group	51	1.07	0.13	2.27	0.12	1.20
Mean diff. between Groups		0.02		1.43		1.41
Harmonized group	42	1.10	0.11	3.74	0.14	2.64
Intermediate group	48	1.09	0.15	3.70	0.16	2.61
Mean diff. between Groups		0.01		0.04		0.03

Source: Field Survey, 2018

Table 2 reveals the mean self-efficacy belief scores of students in the harmonized,

intermediate and control groups on a paired comparative basis. The data in table 2 show

that the overall mean difference between students in harmonized and control groups was 1.44 in favour of harmonized group. This implies that students in harmonized group had higher self-efficacy belief than students in control group. Similarly, the overall mean difference between students in intermediate and control groups was 1.41 in favour of intermediate group. This implies that students in intermediate group had higher self-efficacy belief than those in control group. In the same vein, the overall mean difference between students in harmonized and intermediate groups was 0.03. This difference is in favour of harmonized group. This implies that students in harmonized group had higher

self-efficacy belief than their counterparts in intermediate group. Thus, it can be concluded that the more frequently practical is conducted along with theory lessons in Biology; the more students' self-efficacy belief in solving Biology related problem is enhanced.

Hypothesis one

There is no significant difference in the mean motivation scores among students in the harmonized, intermediate and control groups. The test to hypothesis one is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: ANCOVA Result for Mean Motivation Scores among Students in the Harmonized, Intermediate and Control groups

Source	Type III sum of square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected model	3731.001 ^a	3	372.009	178.010	.000	.564
Intercept	1490.001	1	1490.001	170.101	.000	.532
TPrBMQ	198.090	1	198.090	101.001	.000	.413
Group	2652.100	2	2652.100	368.100	.000	.656
Error	529.007	135	3.890			
Total	299015.101	141				
Corrected Total	3972.000	140				

a. R squared = .114 (Adjusted R Squared= .091)

Source: Field Survey, 2018

Table 3 presents the ANCOVA result for mean motivation scores of students in the harmonized, intermediate and control groups. The data in table 3 reveal that the observed mean difference in the motivation scores among the groups was significant [$F_{2, 135}=368.100$, $P<0.05$]. Hence, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the mean motivation scores of students in the harmonized, intermediate and control groups was rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference in the

mean motivation scores among the groups. Meanwhile, the effect size was 0.656 as indicated by the corresponding partial eta squared value which Cohen cited in Pallant (2014) considered as large effect size. This implies that, 65.6% of the difference or variance in the motivation scores among the groups was explained by the numbers of practical work conducted along with theory lessons in Biology. Hence, the difference in the motivation scores among the groups has a large statistical effect size.

Table 4: Bonferroni Post Hoc Comparison for Mean Motivation Scores among Students in the Harmonized, Intermediate and Control groups

(I) Group	(J) Group	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sign.
HG	CG	12.100*	5.76	.000
IG	CG	21.105*	5.17	.000
IG	HG	9.005*	5.28	.000

Source: Field Survey, 2018

Table 4 shows Bonferroni Post Hoc comparison for mean motivation scores among Students in the Harmonize group (HG), Intermediate group (IG) and Control group (CG). The results reveal that the mean difference (I-J) between H Gand CG is 12.100* and this is significant at $p < 0.05$. This implies that there is a significant difference in the mean motivation scores among students in the harmonized and control groups in favour of harmonized group. This implies that students taught practical with theory more frequently had higher motivation than those taught theory without practical. Likewise, the results reveal that the mean difference (I-J) between IG and CG is 21.105* and this is significant at $p < 0.05$. This implies that there is a significant difference in the mean motivation scores among students in the intermediate and control groups in favour of intermediate group. This implies that

students taught theory with only two practical works had higher motivation than those taught without practical.

However, the paired comparison of IG and HG showed a mean difference of 9.005* and this is significant at $p < 0.05$. This indicates that there is a significant difference in the mean motivation scores among students in the intermediate and harmonized groups in favour of harmonized group. It is therefore concluded that there is a significant difference in the mean motivation scores among students in the harmonized, intermediate, and control groups. This implies that students taught practical with theory more frequently had higher motivation than those taught theory with only two practical works. Students taught theory without practical had lower motivation to learn than those in the rest of the groups (intermediate and harmonized groups).

Hypothesis two

There is no significant difference in the mean self-efficacy belief scores among students in the harmonized, intermediate and control groups. The test to hypothesis two is presented in Table 5.

Table 5: ANCOVA Result for Mean Self-Efficacy Belief Scores among Students in the Harmonized, Intermediate and Control groups

Source	Type III sum of square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected model	4387.231 ^a	3	262.900	158.110	.000	.547
Intercept	1697.110	1	1697.110	143.911	.000	.545
TPrBSEBS	189.100	1	189.100	121.001	.000	.442
Group	3257.009	2	3257.009	376.009	.000	.615
Error	342.007	135	8.173			
Total	212000.100	141				
Corrected Total	3561.000	140				

a. R squared = .114 (Adjusted R Squared= .091)

Source: Field Survey, 2018

Table 5 presents the ANCOVA result for mean self-efficacy belief scores of students in the harmonized, intermediate and control groups. The data in table 3 reveal that the observed mean difference in the self-efficacy belief scores among the groups was significant [$F_{2, 135}=376.009, P<0.05$]. Hence, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the mean self-efficacy belief scores of students in the harmonized, intermediate and control groups was rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference in the mean self-

efficacy belief scores among the groups. Meanwhile, the effect size was 0.615 as indicated by the corresponding partial eta squared value which Cohen cited in Pallant (2014) considered as large effect size. This implies that, 61.5% of the difference or variance in the self-efficacy belief scores among the groups was explained by the numbers of practical work conducted along with theory lessons in Biology. Hence, the difference in the self-efficacy belief scores among the groups has a large statistical effect size.

Table 6: Bonferroni Post Hoc Comparison for Mean Self-Efficacy Scores among Students in the Harmonized, Intermediate and Control groups

(I) Group	(J) Group	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sign.
HG	CG	8.100*	4.69	.000
IG	CG	17.005*	4.47	.000
IG	HG	8.905*	4.34	.000

Source: Field Survey, 2018

Table 6 shows Bonferroni Post Hoc comparison for mean self-efficacy belief scores among students in the Harmonize group (HG), Intermediate group (IG) and

Control group (CG). The results reveal that the mean difference (I-J) between HG and CG is 8.100* and this is significant at $p<0.05$. This implies that there is a

significant difference in the mean self-efficacy belief scores among students in the harmonized and control groups in favour of harmonized group. This implies that students taught practical with theory more frequently had higher self-efficacy belief in solving biology related problems than those taught theory without practical.

Likewise, the results reveal that the mean difference (I-J) between IG and CG is 17.005* and this is significant at $p < 0.05$. This implies that there is a significant difference in the mean self-efficacy belief scores among students in the intermediate and control groups in favour of intermediate group. This implies that students taught theory with only two practical works had higher self-efficacy belief than those taught without practical. However, the paired comparison of IG and HG showed a mean difference of 8.905* and this is significant at $p < 0.05$. This indicates that there is a significant difference in the mean self-efficacy belief scores among students in the intermediate and harmonized groups in favour of harmonized group. It is therefore concluded that there is a significant difference in the mean self-efficacy belief scores among students in the harmonized, intermediate, and control groups. This implies that students taught practical with theory more frequently had higher self-efficacy belief than those taught theory with only two practical works. Students taught theory without practical had lower self-efficacy belief in solving biology related problem than those in the rest of the groups (intermediate and harmonized groups).

Discussion of Findings

The study investigated if frequent practical work could enhance senior secondary two (SS2) students' motivation and self-efficacy belief in solving Biology related problem. The findings have revealed that, students in the harmonized group that carried out the practical work more frequently had higher motivation to learn

Biology than their counterparts in the other groups (intermediate and control groups). Meanwhile, the finding also revealed that, students in the intermediate group (only two practical sessions) had higher motivation than their counterparts in the control group (those without any practical). This shows that students in the harmonized group because of frequent practical work carried out had higher motivation than those in the intermediate group while those in the control group had lower motivation compared with any other groups in the study. This shows that frequent practical work with theory aids students to have higher motivation to learn Biology lessons. The finding agrees with that of Akbas, Orhan and Eyduran (2010) who found that repeated measures or frequency of an activity have great effects on animal behaviour and in this case biology students. In the same vein, the finding also agrees with Achor and Agamber (2013) found out that frequent practical works significantly enhance students' psychomotor skill acquisition.

Another major finding of this study is that, students in the harmonized group that carried out the practical work more frequently had higher self-efficacy belief in solving biology related problem than their counterparts in the other groups (intermediate and control groups). Meanwhile, the finding also revealed that, students in the intermediate group (only two practical sessions) had higher self-efficacy belief in solving biology related problem than their counterparts in the control group (those without any practical). This shows that students in the harmonized group because of frequent practical work carried out had higher self-efficacy belief than those in the intermediate group while those in the control group had lower self-efficacy belief in solving biology related problem compared with any other groups in the study. The finding agrees with that of Akbas, Orhan and Eyduran (2010) who found that repeated measures or frequency of an activity have great effects on animal

behaviour and in this case biology students. This shows that frequent practical work with theory aids students to have higher self-efficacy belief in solving biology related problem.

Conclusion

This study has established that the system of teaching theory with practical work to students as frequently as possible is more rewarding and beneficial to students in terms of enhancing motivation. It is also evident from the findings of this study that frequent practical work enhances students' self-efficacy belief in solving biology related problem.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Since, the more frequently practical is conducted along with theory lessons in biology, the more students motivation to learn is enhanced. Therefore, teachers should be encouraged to use frequent practical to enhance students' motivation.
2. Teachers should also be encouraged to use frequent practical work to enhance students' self-efficacy belief.
3. Workshops and seminars should be organized for biology teachers to keep them abreast of the practical work. This will enable them to plan and organize adequately for practical work.
4. School proprietors, principals and the relevant school authorities should find ways of motivating their biology teachers so as to encourage them carryout the practical work as frequently as possible.
5. There should be strict monitoring and supervision by supervisors and school heads to ensure that practical work is

carried out each time it appears on the time table by students to their enhance motivation and self-efficacy belief.

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